

A pulse polarographic method for the determination of primary and secondary amines and its application to the analysis of organic isocyanates

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Abstract : The observations that carbon disulphide transforms primary and secondary amines in acetonitrile medium quantitatively into dithiocarbamates and following their reaction with copper(II) in the same medium, the latter can be successfully determined using pulse-polarography, have been made the basis of a simple, accurate and reliable method for the determination not only of primary and secondary amines but organic isocyanates as well.

Keywords : Primary/secondary amines, organic isocyanates. copper(II), pulse polarography.

Amines and organoisocyanates are compounds of considerable commercial and synthetic importance. Where as amines find their use in industries connected with pharmaceuticals, coatings, adhesives, cosmetics, textiles and dyestuffs¹, organoisocyanates are used as starting materials or intermediates in the synthesis of various types of polymers, detergents and pesticides². In view of the above, the determination of amines and organoisocyanates is of considerable value and scope. We have recently described a differential pulse polarographic method for the determination of dithiocarbamates based on their reaction with copper(II) perchlorate in acetonitrile³. The simplicity, reliability and excellent sensitivity of this method prompted us to extend its use in the first instance to the determination of primary and secondary amines after their quantitative transformation into dithiocarbamates through reaction with carbon disulphide. Further, since an amine transforms an organoisocyanate smoothly and quantitatively into a urea in acetonitrile medium⁴, it was found extremely interesting to utilize the above pulse polarographic method for the determination of organoisocyanates as well. In this method, an isocyanate is reacted with an excess of amine (*n*-butylamine in the present case) in acetonitrile medium produce a substituted urea. The residual amine is measured as *n*-butyldithiocarbamate by pulse polarography in the same manner as described above for amines.

Urea formed and excess carbon disulphide do not interfere in the present method.

Results and discussion

The method developed for the determination of primary and secondary amines is infact based on their transformation with carbon disulphide into dithiocarbamates (alkylammonium (I) in case of primary amines and dialkylammonium dithiocarbamates (II) in case of secondary amines) in acetonitrile medium. The quantitative

formation of such dithiocarbamates through above reactions has already been established in our laboratory⁵. Based on the diffusion-controlled peaks obtained at -95 to -135 mV (Table 1, Fig. 1) resulting from the reaction of amines (as dithiocarbamates) with copper(II), a pulse polarographic method has been evolved for the determination of amines. That the above peaks infact emerge from a copper(III) dithiocarbamates complexes formed as a result of dithiocarbamates-copper(II) reaction, has been clearly shown through mechanistic studies carried out on the above reaction using cyclic voltammetry and pulse polarography³. The electrochemical characteristics of each amine (as dithiocarbamate)-copper(II) reaction are given in Table

Table 1. Differential pulse polarographic and calibration parameters for primary and secondary amines (as dithiocarbamates) in the presence of copper(II) perchlorate in acetonitrile

Amine	E_p (V) vs SCE	Linearity limit (upto $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Slope	Intercept
	(-ve)			
Methyl	0.110	0.90	0.8109	-0.0020
Ethyl	0.120	0.98	0.7184	-0.0227
<i>n</i> -Propyl	0.115	1.18	0.8916	0.0053
<i>n</i> -Butyl	0.100	1.46	1.1802	0.0040
Dimethyl	0.095	0.90	0.7825	-0.0027
Diethyl	0.125	1.46	0.8616	0.0007
Di- <i>n</i> -butyl	0.105	2.58	1.1542	0.0033
Di- <i>n</i> -pentyl	0.135	3.14	1.5758	0.0467

Fig. 1. Typical differential pulse polarogram of *n*-butylamine (as *n*-butylammonium, *n*-butyldithiocarbamate) with copper(II) perchlorate as representative of primary/secondary amines at $23 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$: (1) supporting electrolyte, (2) *n*-butyldithiocarbamate at DME.

1. The determinations have been made on the basis of calibration graphs drawn between the concentration of amine (μg) and peak current (μA). The maximum concentration ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) of each amine up to which its linear-

ity relationship with the current intensity follows is given in Table 1. Using the straight line equation $y = mx + c$, the slope and intercept values have been determined and are given in Table 1. The listed amines with sample sizes 0.3 and 0.9 μg have been determined with maximum relative standard deviation of 0.8% (Table 2). The proposed method possesses advantages over acidimetric method (commonly used for analysing amines) in that tertiary amines and other basic compounds do not interfere and the method can be used at microanalytical level.

With regards to the determination of organoisocyanates, it may be mentioned that *n*-butylamine (used for transformation of an isocyanate into ureas) gives a diffusion controlled peaks at -100 mV (Fig. 1, Table 1). That this peak in fact emerges from the *n*-butyl dithiocarbamate-copper(II) reaction is evident. The proposed method (non-aqueous) for analysing isocyanates is advantageous in that organoisocyanates react with water and that restrict their determination in aqueous medium⁶.

The listed organic isocyanates, with sample sizes 1.0 and 4.0 μg , have been determined with maximum relative standard deviation of 1.0% (Table 2).

Experimental

Acetonitrile (Merck) was distilled twice from phosphorous(V) oxide (5 g L^{-1}). Dimethylformamide (Merck) was purified by storage over anhydrous sodium carbonate for 2 days. The solvent was decanted off, distilled and the fraction distilling at $148.5\text{--}149.5^\circ\text{C}$ collected and stored in a brown bottle. Tetraethylammonium perchlorate (TEAP, 0.01 *M* in acetonitrile) and standard solution of copper(II) perchlorate in acetonitrile were pre-

Table 2. Differential pulse polarographic determination of some primary and secondary amines and organic isocyanates with copper(II) perchlorate

Amines	Primary and secondary amines		Isocyanates	Organic isocyanates	
	Amount taken = 0.3 μg	Amount taken = 0.9 μg		Amount taken = 1.0 μg	Amount taken = 4.0 μg
Methyl	0.299 ± 0.001	0.905 ± 0.004	<i>n</i> -Butyl	1.01 ± 0.007	3.98 ± 0.045
Ethyl	0.298 ± 0.002	0.898 ± 0.006	Phenyl	0.99 ± 0.004	3.96 ± 0.035
<i>n</i> -Propyl	0.301 ± 0.001	0.906 ± 0.008	Cyclohexyl	1.02 ± 0.009	4.04 ± 0.034
<i>n</i> -Butyl	0.298 ± 0.003	0.901 ± 0.005	Hexamethylene diisocyanate	0.98 ± 0.006	4.02 ± 0.029
Dimethyl	0.298 ± 0.002	0.897 ± 0.006	Methylene diphenyl diisocyanate	1.01 ± 0.010	3.96 ± 0.031
Diethyl	0.299 ± 0.002	0.906 ± 0.009			
Di- <i>n</i> -butyl	0.298 ± 0.001	0.895 ± 0.007			
Di- <i>n</i> -pentyl	0.302 ± 0.003	0.896 ± 0.006			

Values are means of five determinations with standard deviation (\pm).

pared as described earlier³. Methylamine (40% aqueous solution), ethylamine (50% aqueous solution), dimethylamine (40% aqueous solution), diethylamine (60% aqueous solution) (all Merck) and *n*-butylamine, di-*n*-butylamine and di-*n*-pentylamine (all Fluka) were used. The purity of each amine was checked by known methods⁷. *n*-Butyl-, phenyl-, cyclohexylisocyanates and hexamethylenediisocyanate, methylene diphenyldiisocyanate (all Merck) were used. The purity of each isocyanate was checked by known methods⁴. Triton-X-100 (Merck), 0.002% solution in acetonitrile, was used as suppressor.

The polarographic measurements were made at 23 °C in an inert atmosphere achieved by purging nitrogen for 5 min, with an Elico (India) Pulse polarograph (Model CL-90) equipped with DME as working electrode, SCE as reference electrode and coiled platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode with the following instrumental parameters; initial potential = 400 mV; drop time = 1 s; pulse amplitude = 50 mV; sensitivity = 1 µA/V; X-axis = 100 mV/cm; and Y-axis = 200 mV/cm (on polarocord).

For the determination of primary and secondary amines :

Aliquots (0.5–4.0 ml) of acetonitrile solution (10^{-3} M) of each amine were taken in a 50 ml glass-stoppered measuring flask, mixed with a drop (~ 50 µL) of carbon disulphide and the volume made to 20 ml with acetonitrile. The resulting solution was mixed with 5.0 ml of copper(II) perchlorate (0.001 M in acetonitrile), 2.0 ml of Triton-X-100 (0.002% in acetonitrile) and the final volume made to the mark with TEAP (0.01 M in acetonitrile). The solution in each case was transferred to a polarographic cell and nitrogen gas was passed for 5 min. The differential pulse polarogram of each solution was recorded in the same manner as described above. Calibration graphs were constructed by plotting peak current (µA) versus concentration of amine added to copper(II) perchlorate. The electrochemical characteristics are given in Table 1.

For the determination of organic isocyanates :

Aliquots of solutions of each isocyanate in acetonitrile (dimethylformamide in case of methylene diphenyldiisocyanate) were added with stirring to 5.0 ml of *n*-butylamine (0.001 M in acetonitrile) taken in a 50 ml glass stoppered measuring flasks and the volume made to 20 ml with acetonitrile. The flasks were stoppered, swirled to mix the reactants and set aside for 10 min to complete the reaction. Each solution was mixed with a drop of carbon disulphide (to transform the amine into a dithiocarbamate), 5.0 ml of copper(II) perchlorate (0.001 M in acetonitrile) and 2.0 ml of Triton-X-100 (0.002% in acetonitrile) and the final volume made to the mark with TEAP. The solution in each case was transferred to a polarographic cell and differential pulse polarogram recorded in the same manner as described above. The peak current values thus obtained were referred to standard values obtained with pure *n*-butylamine to determine the amount of organic isocyanate.

References

1. S. A. Lawrence, "Amines – Synthesis, Properties and Applications", Mimas Ltd., 2004, pp. 265-305.
2. S. Patai, "The Chemistry of Cyanates and their Thioderivatives", Part-I and II, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1977, pp. 620-652.
3. D. K. Sharma, A. Gupta, S. Kumar and B. C. Verma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 20.
4. D. K. Sharma and R. D. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 1104.
5. B. C. Verma, B. G. Rao, P. Kumar, N. K. Sharma, D. K. Sharma and N. Sharma, *Nat. Acad. Sci. Lett.*, 1988, **11**, 179; B. C. Verma, S. Chauhan, N. Sharma, U. Sharma, D. K. Sharma and A. Sood, *Talanta*, 1986, **33**, 703; B. C. Verma, R. K. Sood, S. Chauhan, A. Sood, N. K. Sharma and D. K. Sharma, *Proc. Ind. Nat. Sci. Acad.*, 1986, **52A**, 1420.
6. M. R. F. Ashworth, "The Determination of Sulphur-containing Groups", Academic Press, London, New York, 1972, **1**, 124.
7. D. K. Sharma and R. D. Sharma, *Talanta*, 1991, **38**, 665.